

1 Supplementary Information 1

2 Supplementary Information to:
3 Hypothetical Extraction Method in Life Cycle Assessment: Method and
4 uses

5
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11

12 **Summary:** This Supplementary Information has seven subsections, the first discusses
13 some mathematical similarities and differences between Input Output Analysis and Life
14 Cycle Assessment. The second discusses various options to extract processes with
15 Hypothetical Extraction Method. The third discusses a special case of extracting the
16 Functional Unit as a process. The fourth discusses a nuance between subtracting scaling
17 vectors or inventory matrices and why we suggest using the latter. The fifth discusses the
18 stability of HEM calculations. The sixth discusses some important nuances in interpreting
19 Path contributions. Finally, the seventh shows both a Sankey diagram of the ecoinvent case
20 and some discussion about its interpretation and an additional example making use of HEM
21 to extract a location. All sections are listed in the table of contents below.

22

23 **Abbreviations**

CA	Contribution Analysis
EF	Elementary Flow
FU	Functional Unit
HEM	Hypothetical Extraction Method
IOA	Input Output Analysis
IO-LCA	Input Output-LCA
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
SI	Supplementary Information

24

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43 1. Hypothetical Extraction Method in Life Cycle 44 Assessment

45 1.1. IOA, IO-LCA and Process-LCA

46 Input Output Analysis (IOA), Input-Output Life Cycle Assessment (IO-LCA) and Process-LCA
47 (pLCA) are three methods that are closely related to each other. While we will not get into
48 their extensive histories and nuances here, we will discuss some mathematical differences.

49 IOA is an important method where it is often required to calculate the Leontief Inverse $L =$
50 $(I - A)^{-1}$ (Leontief, 1936) which helps find how much of everything is produced in an
51 economy to satisfy final demand. In pLCA (Heijungs et al., 2022), we use a similar inverse
52 A^{-1} which directly inverts the technology matrix without first subtracting A from an identity
53 matrix. Some researchers prefer to use a mid-way point between IOA and LCA and use IO-
54 LCA, which also makes use of $(I - A)^{-1}$. The nuances between these two approaches to
55 LCA are discussed in detail by Heijungs et al. (2022).

56 The main difference between $(I - A)^{-1}$ (IO-LCA) and A^{-1} (pLCA) is how production is
57 modeled. If a process were to consume some of its own product directly (e.g. howecoinvent
58 (Wernet et al., 2016) model efficiency loss in electricity markets), we can clearly see a
59 difference. IO-LCA would model the output as e.g. 0.01 kWh for a production of 1kWh and a
60 loss of 1%, where pLCA would model this as a production of 0.99 kWh. As in IO-LCA the 0.01
61 would be subtracted from 1 (in I), the end result would be the same, but the modelling is
62 different. In case a process would not consume from itself, it would simply be '0' in IO-LCA,
63 where in pLCA it would simply have its production amount.

64 This becomes important when we consider the extraction of processes. When extracting a
65 process, in IO-LCA, the production can be set to '0', as it would simply subtract '0' from 1
66 (in I), but for pLCA, setting the production to '0' would mean a process that produces
67 nothing, which is not possible in the existing mathematical structure -logically, a process
68 producing nothing does not contribute to the economy and should not be considered as part
69 of the system-.

70 1.2. Options to extract processes

71 Miller and Lahr (2001) list seven options to do Hypothetical Extraction Method (HEM). Three
72 of the options Miller and Lahr (2001) discuss rely on the extraction of production. As
73 discussed above, options that extract the production of a process are not possible in
74 pLCA. As such, we are left with four options in pLCA, as listed in Table 1. In case 1, the entire
75 process is removed from the matrix, thus shrinking the technology matrix. While this option

76 works in practice, in combination with process-contributions, this approach becomes
 77 challenging to perform in practice as the resulting matrices have different sizes, as is also
 78 demonstrated in Supplementary Information (SI) 2.2.

79 In addition to the main text, we show an abstract format of the technology matrix in Table 1.
 80 The example extracts the top-left process as *target*. This representation shows the parts of
 81 the matrix that are extracted with 0 and the parts of the matrix that remain as ■. Originally,
 82 Miller and Lahr (2001) take a more complex approach with creating matrix partitions and
 83 inverting the partitions separately instead of as a whole. In LCA, we see no reason to do this
 84 currently.

85 *Table 1: Options to extract processes for HEM in LCA. The numbering of the cases is the same as in Miller and Lahr (2001).*

Case	Technology matrix	Description
1	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \blacksquare \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow [\blacksquare]$	Extracting the processes from the technology matrix, decreasing its size (deleting both the rows and columns).
2a	$\begin{bmatrix} \blacksquare & 0 \\ 0 & \blacksquare \end{bmatrix}$	Extracting both <i>consumers</i> (row values) and <i>consumption</i> (column values) of the <i>target</i> processes, resulting in processes that are both un-used and ‘empty’ (replacing all process flow values except reference flow with 0).
3a	$\begin{bmatrix} \blacksquare & 0 \\ \blacksquare & \blacksquare \end{bmatrix}$	Extracting all <i>consumers</i> (row values) of the <i>target</i> processes in the technology matrix, resulting in processes that are un-used (replacing all process flows <i>from</i> this process with 0).
3b	$\begin{bmatrix} \blacksquare & \blacksquare \\ 0 & \blacksquare \end{bmatrix}$	Extracting all <i>consumption</i> (column values) of the <i>target</i> processes in the technology matrix, resulting in ‘empty’ processes (replacing all process flows <i>to</i> this process with 0).

86
 87 In Figure 1 the options from above are shown for the example case, extracting ‘electricity
 88 production’ from the system. In SI 2.2, we present results and calculation steps for each of
 89 the four cases from Table 1 and Figure 1. In cases where the Functional Unit (FU) is not part
 90 of the extracted processes, all four cases would return the same result. Only in cases where
 91 the FU is also extracted do we get different results, as discussed in section 1.3 below.

92 The results for these cases would be the same for two reasons: Firstly, the Elementary Flows
 93 (EFs) would be removed (Case 1) or zero (Cases 2a, 3a and 3b). Secondly, If the FU is in the
 94 *remaining* system, there cannot be any intermediate flows from the *target* system to or from
 95 the *remaining* system. In Case 1, the *target* processes are removed entirely and thus cannot
 96 have any contribution. In Cases 2a and 3a, the reference flows from the *target* processes are
 97 not consumed by other processes and cannot contribute to any *remaining* processes if they
 98 are not consumed. Finally in Cases 2a and Case 3b, the *target* processes do not consume

99 anything from the *remaining* system and do not have any EFs (reason 1), they cannot
 100 contribute to the *remaining* system.

101 Together, these two reasons mean that in all four cases the *target* processes cannot
 102 contribute to the *remaining* system through two separate reasons. As the contribution of the
 103 *target* is defined as the subtraction of the *remaining* system inventory from the *original*
 104 system inventory (eq. (7) in the main text), the results for both the *target* processes inventory
 105 and *remaining* system inventory would be the same for all cases.

106 From our discussion above and shown in SI 2.2. we find that the total results are the same
 107 for all four cases. In the cases 2a, 3a and 3b we can also apply process Contribution Analysis
 108 (CA) to both the *remaining* and *target* results, where this is not practical with case 1.

109

110 *Figure 1. The four case options to extract a process from the system, shown both as the technology matrix as well as the*
 111 *system. In the system flowcharts, white boxes show the remaining system, yellow the target process and orange arrows*
 112 *indicate extracted flows. Note that only the technology matrix A is shown, in all extraction cases, the elementary flow matrix*
 113 *B would be removed (Case 1) or zero (other cases) for the extracted processes.*

114 1.3. Extracting the Functional Unit

115 It could happen in an analysis that the practitioner wants to extract the processes that
116 provide the FU. This is shown in Figure 2 for the case study with steel production removed.
117 The calculations are shown in SI 2.3 for all four cases discussed earlier. In case 1, this would
118 be impossible, as the process is entirely removed. In cases 2a and 3b, with the consumption
119 of FU process set to 0, the scaling vector for the *remaining* system would be 0 (except the
120 FU), together with zero EFs, the inventory and subsequent impact results would be 0. As the
121 FU process would not consume anything anymore -the consumption is now zeroes-, the
122 extracted *target* process would never have indirect contributions. 100% of the contribution
123 would be from the *target* in these two cases, as we also see in SI 2.3.

124 In Case 3a, the consumption of the target FU would still consume from the *remaining* system.
125 As the *remaining* system in turn does not consume from the extracted *target* processes, the
126 scaling vector for the *remaining system* would become only the intermediate products
127 directly required for the production of the FU. In the example, this would mean that the
128 production of 1kg of steel is considered, without the additional demands for steel from other
129 processes (e.g. the production of steel for the power plant for electricity production). In
130 other words; only the consumption of steel was extracted from the technology matrix, but
131 not from the FU.

132 As shown in SI 2.3, this results in a contribution of 24% of the *remaining* system and a
133 contribution of 76% of the *target* processes. The contribution of the *remaining* system would
134 include all the contributions from the processes ‘Coal mining’, ‘Electricity production’ and
135 ‘Iron ore mining’ for that direct production to fulfil the FU. The contribution of the *target*
136 processes would include the direct contribution of the steel, plus the contribution from all
137 steel that would have been indirectly needed in steel consumption in the *remaining* system.

138 While Case 3a could seem more complex to interpret at first, the results are better linked to
139 the differentiation of the *target* and *remaining* distinction. The goal of HEM is to assess the
140 effect of processes on other processes. With Case 3a, we can still assess the effects of the
141 *target* processes and the *remaining* system, while with cases 2a and 3b, this would
142 disappear and we would only be left with a 100% contribution from the *target*. This is why
143 Case 3a is suggested as the default, though practitioners may want to experiment with
144 cases 2a or 3b as well if their specific use case benefits this.

145

Case System change

146

147 *Figure 2. The four cases to extract a process from the system for the FU of the case study, shown both as the technology*
 148 *matrix as well as the system. In the system flowcharts, white boxes show the remaining system, yellow the target process*
 149 *and orange arrows indicate extracted flows. Note that only the technology matrix A is shown, in all extraction cases, the*
 150 *elementary flow matrix B would be removed (Case 1) or zero (other cases) for the extracted processes.*

151 1.4. Extracting the scaling vector vs extracting the inventory

152 The reason we subtract the inventories instead of the scaling vectors, is because of the EF
 153 matrices B and B^* . Where in IOA, we are often interested in the actual economic structure
 154 of results, in LCA, we are mainly interested in the inventory results and characterized results.
 155 Because we make changes to the EF matrix B^* for the *remaining* system, they would affect
 156 the inventory g^* independently from the scaling vector s^* . While we can subtract the scaling
 157 vectors similarly to presented in the main text, this would only hold for comparisons of the
 158 scaling vectors, or in cases where B would remain unchanged. When case 3a is used and
 159 the FU is part of the extracted processes, the results would differ because of the changes
 160 to B^* .

161 1.5. Stability of HEM results

162 Another important difference between IOA and process-LCA that was not discussed yet are
163 that technology matrices are often sparsely populated¹, meaning they have relatively few
164 numbers that are not 0. Consider for example the ecoinvent database (Wernet et al., 2016),
165 which has ~20000 processes, meaning the matrix A has a size of ~20000 * ~20000
166 processes, with ~400 million possible flows between those processes, while most
167 processes have on the order of tens or maximum hundreds of flows, this leaves many zeroes.
168 In general, roughly ~500000 flows are non-zero, leading to a ‘fill rate’ of ~0.125%. Matrix
169 sparsity generally comes with certain risks where a matrix may not be inverted anymore,
170 meaning the LCA would not be solvable through regular means. However, as is extensively
171 discussed by Heijungs & Suh (2002, Ch. 10), this is generally not a problem in Life Cycle
172 Inventory (LCI) databases due to the nature of the LCI data.

173 It should be noted that some LCA software makes use of solvers² instead of true matrix
174 inversion to calculate the scaling vector s . In practice this has not shown to be a problem for
175 matrix stability, and these will be assumed to be the same operation for the purposes of this
176 discussion.

177 As extractions from the technology matrix A are made, sparsity increases, the question
178 arises how this affects the invertibility of the technology matrix. As we see in Figure 1 and
179 Figure 2, some flows are removed, this happens with the specific goal of isolating the *target*
180 processes from the *remaining* system. As we only solve the *original* and *remaining* system
181 (the *target* inventory g^0 is calculated from the other inventories, not calculated through
182 inversion), we are only concerned about the invertibility of A^* .

183 The *remaining* system essentially gets ‘isolated’ processes where they are extracted. In
184 cases 1 and 2a above, this means these processes do not affect the inversion, in cases 3a
185 and 3b, this means these processes either have no end users (3a) or no consumption (3b).
186 Both already happen often in large databases such as the ecoinvent database. The former
187 happens when a process is meant primarily for practitioners (e.g. the production of some
188 foods), the latter happens often with the cut-off system model, where a recycled product
189 comes with zero burdens (no consumption/inputs). Thus logically, the creation of more of
190 these processes should not meaningfully affect the invertibility of the matrix. If the *original*
191 system is invertible, there should be no reason why the *remaining* system would not be.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sparse_matrix

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LU_decomposition

192 We also demonstrate the stability of this approach with a sensitivity analysis shown in SI 2.4,
193 where different changes are made to the system, showing the stability of this approach
194 under different circumstances.

195 1.6. Path Contributions

196 Path contributions have been extensively covered in Srocka & Montiel (2021) and van der
197 Meide et al. (2025). As demonstrated by van der Meide et al. (2025), interpretation of Path
198 contribution results has been challenging. Since then, the author has been in personal
199 contact with M. Srocka (May & June 2025) and the method has been adjusted slightly. The
200 new approach is presented in SI 2.6 and SI 2.7. The main change is that all flows are scaled
201 individually instead of all flows being scaled to the FU. According to M. Srocka this change
202 should be more correct. The updated algorithm authored by M. Srocka is presented in sec.
203 1.6.1.

204 As shown in Table 3 in the main text, the results still require caution with interpretation. The
205 results seem to indicate that the contribution of ‘Electricity’ would be lower than the total
206 direct process contribution at that place in the system, which indicates that the algorithm
207 reassigns part of a process’ own direct emissions to the processes feeding it, which could
208 potentially be interpreted as ‘under-counting’ the impact from ‘Electricity’. The example
209 system does not have flows producing negative results for the impact category ‘Climate
210 change’, so the ‘path contribution’ results should never be lower than process contributions
211 for that process.

212 Additionally, as the formulas for calculating results for path contributions have changed,
213 they now provide different answers as well. This poses an additional challenge, where
214 different software will have different approaches to ‘path contributions’. ‘Graph traversal’ in
215 Brightway2 (Mutel, 2017) did find the same results as path contributions as presented in
216 Srocka & Montiel (2021). The Sankey calculation in OpenLCA 2 by GreenDelta (2023) seems
217 to make use of the updated algorithm shared by M. Srocka. The correctness of path or
218 Sankey algorithms in non-open software are impossible to verify due to their closed nature,
219 which should be of concern for scientists and LCA practitioners that care about the
220 replicability of their work.

221 1.6.1. Updated algorithm

222 This text for the updated algorithm is adapted from SI 1.6 of van der Meide et al. (2025) for
223 the revised algorithm.

224 The relative fractions of intermediate flows c between the processes can be calculated as
225 follows:

$$c = - \frac{s_{j_x} \cdot a_{j_1, j_x}}{s_{j_1} \cdot a_{j_1, j_1}} \quad (1)$$

226

227 Next, an intensity matrix \mathbf{M} is calculated from \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{A}^{-1} :

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{B} \mathbf{A}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

228

229 Then, \mathbf{t} , the total requirement is calculated based on the element-wise multiplication of the
 230 scaling vector \mathbf{s} over the diagonal values in \mathbf{A} . Diagonalizing means putting the values of the
 231 respective vector on the diagonal of a square $\mathbf{0}$ matrix of the same size.

$$\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{s} \odot \text{diag}(\mathbf{A}) \quad (3)$$

232

233 Then, a correction factor λ_j is calculated for each process j in the system.

$$\lambda_j = \frac{1}{\mathbf{A}_{jj} \mathbf{A}_{jj}^{-1}} \quad (4)$$

234

235 The total requirement \mathbf{t} is multiplied element-wise by the correction factor λ to get the
 236 totality factors τ .

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{t} \odot \boldsymbol{\lambda} \quad (5)$$

237

238 Through multiplying the intensity matrix \mathbf{M} and the totality factors $\boldsymbol{\tau}$, the upstream results \mathbf{U}
 239 are calculated:

$$\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{M} \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\tau}) \quad (6)$$

240

241 Now, we can take any row \mathbf{u}_i in \mathbf{U} and combine it with the relative fractions \mathbf{C} to find the path
 242 contributions for that EF. Where Srocka & Montiel (2021) provide an algorithm for this, we
 243 can also calculate the whole graph at once using matrix multiplication:

$$\mathbf{P}_i = \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_i) \mathbf{C} \quad (7)$$

244

245 \mathbf{U} has all biosphere flows (rows), just as \mathbf{G} from eq. (5) from the main text and while Srocka
 246 & Montiel (2021) focus mainly on inventory results, \mathbf{U} can also be characterized for any
 247 impact category \mathbf{q}^T , which we show below:

$$\mathbf{u}_q = \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{U} \quad (8)$$

248 The change between the previous and this algorithm is that the totality factors τ now replace
249 a correction factor c_r , which was only applied to the reference flow, where τ applies to every
250 process with a unique amount. This is meant to avoid double counting loop contributions.

251 1.6.2. Path contributions in another case

252 In SI 2.7, the original case with three processes of Srocka & Montiel (2021) is replicated
253 based on the updated algorithm presented in sec. 1.6.1, one additional EF is also added to
254 allow further interpretation of the system. Here, it is shown that EF1 for a FU of 2 'Q' has a
255 total impact of 21.27 (which aligns with a regular inventory calculation). To that total, the
256 flow from process 'P' to process 'Q' contributes 0.13 and the flow from process 'R' to
257 process 'Q' contributes 9.19. That implies that 11.95 (21.27 - (0.13 + 9.19)) is the direct
258 impact from process 'Q', while the inventory calculation finds a value of 12.92. Process 'Q'
259 also has 'outgoing' contributions back to the processes 'P' and 'R' of 0.34 and 1.17
260 respectively as well, though it remains unclear how this could resolve the missing impact
261 balance.

262 EF 3 was specifically added to this case to gain more insight into the method, being
263 emitted only by process 'P'. Here we observe similar problems, for example, the balance in
264 process 'P' seems incorrect, as 100% of the impact is created there but still the flow from
265 process 'Q' to 'P' contributes 1.6%, furthermore, the contributions to the FU process 'Q' are
266 higher than 100%. Just like our case, this case also leaves questions to the correct
267 interpretation of these contribution results.

268 1.6.3. Comparing Path contributions when extracting multiple processes

269 Extracting multiple processes is possible with HEM, this is not directly possible with Path
270 contributions. Path contributions allow a practitioner to assess as the direct and indirect
271 contribution from a single process, this can be combined for multiple processes
272 sequentially, but these contribution results cannot be summed without possible double
273 counting. Consider for example the processes 'electricity production' and 'steel production'
274 in the example case. In this example, steel is consumed for the production of electricity, this
275 would mean that the path contribution of electricity already contains part of the contribution
276 for steel. Inversely, electricity is not consumed directly in steel production (in this example,
277 not in reality), however, electricity still contributes indirectly through the consumed coal and
278 iron ore. This means that if the contributions from 'electricity' and 'steel' is simply summed,
279 this would over-count the result, as both would partially contain impacts from the other
280 process.

281 1.7. Ecoinvent example case

282 1.7.1. Path contributions

283 In our example case, we also present a Sankey diagram in Figure 3 below. This shows only a
284 minor part of the entire system contributing to impacts for the production of copper. As
285 shown, the top mining processes have no direct contributions themselves, but still
286 contribute 9.87% and 9.83% due to their connector role. Where interpretation becomes
287 more complex is that this ‘flow’ is then combined into a market and split again to various
288 smelting processes. Additionally, there is also an entire copper production chain from
289 ‘copper, cathode, solvent extraction and electrowinning’ where only this last process is
290 shown. This Sankey figure demonstrates the challenges of interpreting the contribution of
291 complex supply chains without double counting.

292 1.7.2. Extraction of China as location

293 Here, we apply a different HEM scenario to the same example ecoinvent case as the main
294 text. We find the results in Figure 4 below and are also shown in SI 2.10. In Figure 4 A. we see
295 that the *target* ‘China’ contributes about 41% of the impact. Figure 4 A also shows process
296 group contributions (grouped by location) from the three highest impact locations to both
297 the *target* and the *remaining* groups. This shows us that ‘GLO’ (Global) and ‘RoW’ (Rest of
298 World) locations are major contributors to both the *target* and the *remaining* groups.
299 However, we also see that while China contributes 41% of the impact of copper when
300 including both direct and indirect contributions, the direct contribution to the total is only
301 24% (or ~60% of the HEM contribution). From Figure 3 we can see some processing takes
302 place in China (smelting of copper concentrate, sulfide ore CN), though the sulfide ore
303 comes from different locations (Chile (CL) and Rest of World (RoW)).

304 Again comparing to other contribution approaches, Figure 4 B and C show different
305 contributions for the *target* and *remaining* groups and a different spread again for the
306 grouped locations.

307

308

309 *Figure 3. Sankey of Path contributions for 1kg copper from 'Market for copper, Cathode, GLO'.*

310

311

Ecoinvent: Comparison of HEM extraction of 'China' to other Contribution Analysis approaches

312

313 *Figure 4. Contribution Analysis results for different approaches for the production of 1kg 'copper, cathode' and the*
 314 *extraction/contribution of 'China' as location in ecoinvent. The bottom numbers are in percentage contribution. A:*
 315 *Contribution of both the target processes and remaining system. Also showing the grouped process contributions to the*
 316 *target and remaining system. Grouped by location name, showing highest three contributing locations and 'rest'. B:*
 317 *Grouped process contributions, grouped by 'target' and 'remaining'. C: Grouped process contributions, grouped by*
 318 *location name, showing highest three contributing locations and 'rest'. The following ecoinvent location abbreviations have*
 319 *been used: CN; China, RoW; Rest of World, GLO; Global, IN; India.*

320 While this perspective with different locations can provide interesting insights, we also see
 321 that the information that can be gained relies on the data quality. Ecoinvent does have
 322 production location and trade information, but we also see that the quality of this data may
 323 be lacking and not always be provide real insight. As shown in Figure 4, 37% of the
 324 contribution comes from 'GLO' and 'RoW'. In reality, these processes would happen in real
 325 countries, but these generalized datasets do not provide useable insight. However,
 326 ecoinvent has been making progress in this regard since recent (3.10+) versions with the
 327 inclusion of 'import' processes for some commodities. These represent trade between
 328 different locations and could make the assessment we show above more insightful,
 329 providing this is implemented more extensively within the ecoinvent database. Despite this,
 330 the classical use case regional extraction with HEM in IOA does not yet translate well to LCA.

331

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